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Characterization Of Some Selected Granite Rocks As Thermal Energy Storage Materials

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to characterize the granite samples from Wara, Yauri and Zuru in order to find one with better properties for thermal storage materials. The chemical analysis is carried out using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis and the results for chemical analysis shows that all granite samples have similar chemical composition, with variation in proportion of the element. The thermal properties were study using Differential scanning Calorimetric (DSC). The specific heat capacity of granite measures at 25 °C is 790 KJ/KG and found to be same value for all samples but the latent heat varies with corresponding value of 0.5923 KJ/KG, 0.4343 KJ/KG and 0.631KJ/KG for Wara, Yawuri and Zuru respectively. The thermal conductivity of the samples was found to be 2.99 w/mk, 2.12 w/mk and 3.12 w/mk respectively, which signifies, Zuru granite sample to be selected for thermal storage for its better thermal properties.

Keywords: Thermal Energy, Storage Materials, Granite Rocks, specific heat capacity, ceramic and chemical composition

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Steady rise in fuel prices and greenhouse gas emissions are the major motivating factors towards utilizing more efficient renewable energy sources. Solar energy is regarded as single and ultimate energy sources in many parts of the world. Researchers are looking for novel, sustainable energy source all across the globe. The development of energy storage devices is a critical option that is equally important as the creation of novel energy sources. A pressing challenge for technologists is the thermal storage in suitable forms that can be normally transformed into the requisite structure. Thermal storage assumes a pivotal role in energy preservation by mitigating the imbalance between supply and demand whilst augmenting the efficiency and dependability of thermal energy (Sharma *et al.*, 2023).

The utilization of solar energy holds significant importance as a sustainable energy resource in the modern world, due to its extensive availability and abundance. In this regard, Nigeria is endowed with exceptional Direct Normal Irradiation (DNI) conditions, hence presenting an ideal location for the harnessing of solar energy (Nahhas, Tamar, Xavier, Py & Najim Sadiki, 2022). However, the intermittency of solar energy, as is the case with other renewable energy sources, poses a significant challenge. The reason for this is that solar energy is exclusively obtainable during diurnal hours and is susceptible to meteorological conditions. Elevated temperature Thermal Energy Storage (TES) is becoming increasingly well-known as a vital technology for both industrial applications and solar-powered systems (Shang *et al.*, 2023). The synchronization and harmony of energy supply and demand are made possible by the use of Thermal Energy Storage (TES) technology. Additionally, TES systems are renowned for their extremely high operating efficiency and for having relatively low capital costs in comparison to other storage technologies. These devices function by charging during the day and discharging the built-up heat at night. Sensible Heat Storage (SHS), Latent Heat Storage (LHS), and Thermo-Chemical Storage are the three main categories of TES systems. Sensible Heat Storage systems, are able to store energy unchanged in its initial phase through heating or cooling a liquid or solid storage medium. Many advantages are associated with these systems, including their straightforward construction, cost-effectiveness, and established maturity in the energy storage market. The fact that Sensible Heat Storage (SHS) systems are presently the most widely used thermal energy storage technology and water is a particularly attractive choice for the liquid medium due to its low cost (Sharma *et al.*, 2023).

Granites, with their diverse chemical compositions and grain sizes, are widely distributed and commonly found in various geo-tectonic environments, thus establishing their dominance (Kakoko *et al.*, 2023). Numerous examinations into the unique characteristics of granite have been conducted, demonstrating substantial variations in its characteristics. For instance, Kakoko *et al.* (2023) examined fine- to medium-grained Chinese granite rocks and found that hydrothermal minerals such as feldspar, quartz, pyroxene, and illite were absent. However, when Kakoko *et al.* (2023), examined Moroccan granite samples, they discovered hydrothermal mica that resembled the granite boulders.

Due to the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources, storage is necessary, in order to bridge the gap between the supply and demand of energy. Some of the material used for energy storage suffer in one way or the other such as; Solid-Liquid Phase Change Materials suffer from higher volumetric expansion, Solid- Liquid PCMs in some cases, pose corrosion issues with containers when expose to the oxygen, other problems associated with solid-liquid PCMs include super cooling, instability which can lead to phase decomposition, improper solidification and superheating, in order to avoid all these problems in storage, a solid material is required. Using solid material is important in order to obtain material with better properties required for the storage. For this granite rock is used because their chemical and thermal properties are better for thermal storage and they are cheap and available to the local farmers (Kenisarinet *et al.*, 2020).

The significance of this research lies in its reliance on locally available materials which are also cheap. These materials pose no hazard to the environment, as such they can be utilized by many farmers within the study area. The materials are comparatively available, though neglected and economically feasible, thereby enabling local farmers to incorporate this technology into their Thermal Storage Technology. The aimed of this research is investigate the potentials of granite rock samples from the study area as effective Thermal Energy Storage (TES) material. It has the following objectives: to determine the thermo-physical characteristic of granite rock samples, to determine the chemical composition and minerals phase granite rock samples (Bello *et al.*, 2023).

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Method of sampling

The granite samples were collected from distinct location within Wara, Yauri and Zuru local governments' area of Kebbi State. The appropriate blending of the aforementioned samples source from various location within the designated area was culminated in the formation of a representative samples.

The cone and quartering system as recommended by the American Society of Testing Materials ASTM 2487 (2006), was utilized to accomplish this objective.

2.2 Chemical Composition of Granite Rock.

The X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) technique, which is commonly employed for identifying various elements in a wide range of minerals, was carried out at the central research laboratories, Umar Musa Yar Adua University, Kastina State, Nigeria (Alva et al., 2022). The ED-XRF was carried out at Umaru Musa Yar Adua University Kastina. The results are presented in graphical form for Wara, Yauri and Zuru as Shown in figures 1 to 3 are the chemical composition of the samples for the location

Figure 1. Chemical Composition for Wara Granite. Figure 2. Chemical Composition for Yauri Granite

2.3 Thermo-Physical Properties of Granite

The assessment of the physical attributes of granite samples entails an examination of multiple traits, including but not limited to, latent heat, specific heat capacity and, thermal conductivity. The American Society for Testing Material (ASTM) methodology was employed to execute this endeavor. Each of the aforementioned properties was assessed through unique measures (Lukman, 2019).

3.0 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 The Chemical Composition of the Samples

Figure 3 Chemical Composition for Zuru Granite

Observation on figure 1 shows that the sample contains major and minor compound as summarized in Table 1

Table 1. Summary of Compound Composition for Wara Granite Sample

Major Compound	Concentration %	Peak (m/A)
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.52	9381
MgO	4.08	5
Al ₂ O ₃	11.33	177
SiO ₂	50.09	3747
K ₂ O	3.25	3423
CaO	2.17	3219
BaO	1.00	0
SrO	1.42	0
Sb ₂ O ₃	1.00	0
Trace of Minor Compound		
CuO	0.0006	20
ZnO	0.0149	34
Ga ₂ O ₃	0.0024	10
HfO ₂	0.0101	11
P ₂ O ₅	0.3738	79
SO ₃	0.0879	48
Cl	0.0080	12
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.0026	21
MnO	0.2288	693

Observation on figure 2 shows that the sample contains major and minor compound as summary in Table 2

Table 2. Summary of Chemical Composition for Yauri Granite Sample

Major Compound	Concentration %	Peak(cps/mA)
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.92	10856
MgO	3.76	5
Al ₂ O ₃	11.83	184
SiO ₂	54.22	4056
K ₂ O	1.39	1462
CaO	3.20	4758
SrO ₂	1.77	128
BaO	1.00	0
Traces of Minor Compounds		
ZnO	0.0166	91
Ga ₂ O ₃	0.0025	35
P ₂ O ₅	0.0248	52
SO ₃	0.1004	55
Cl	0.0054	8
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.0007	1
MnO	0.3130	948
CuO	0.0023	7

Observation on figure 3 shows that the sample contains major and minor compound as summary in Table 3.

Table 3 Summary of Chemical Composition for Zuru Granite Sample

Major Compound	Concentration %	Peak (cps/mA)
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.24	8350
MgO	2.72	3
Al ₂ O ₃	8.72	136
SiO ₂	53.04	3967
K ₂ O	3.27	3448
CaO	1.05	1553
BaO	1.00	0
Trace of Minor Compounds		
CuO	0.0009	3
ZnO	0.0151	83
Ga ₂ O ₃	0.0018	26
Hf ₂ O	0.0008	5
P ₂ O ₅	0.2153	45
SO ₃	0.0334	18
Cl	0.0056	8
Bi ₂ O ₃	0.0475	2
Ag ₂ O	0.0003	0

3.2 DIFFERENTIAL SCANING CALORIMETRY

Figure 4 DSC for Wara Granite

Figure 5 DSC for Yauri Granite

Figure 6 DSC for Zuru Granite

Observation on figure 4 the mass of the sample used for this analysis is 5.3000mg. At the heating rate of 10°C/min. the minimum point heat flows was observed at -3.380 wM with the corresponding temperature of 80.77 °C and maximum at 32.5 wM, with temperature of 2250 °C, the onset temperature is 800 °C and end set 1550 °C, the peak point temperature is 1250°C. The latent heat of the sample is 0.5923 J/kg.

Observation on figure 5 the mass of the sample used for this analysis is 5.3000mg. At the heating rate of 10°C/min. the minimum point heat flows was observed at -2.00 wM with the corresponding temperature of 90 °C and maximum at 13.50 wM, with temperature of 1290 °C, the onset temperature is 800 °C and end set 1400 °C, the peak point temperature is 1350°C. The latent heat of the sample is 0.434 J/kg.

Observation on figure 6 the mass of the sample used for this analysis is 5.3000mg. At the heating rate of 10°C/min. the minimum point heat flows was observed at -3.00 wM with the corresponding temperature of 80 °C and maximum at 56.020wM, with temperature of 2300 °C, the onset temperature is 900 °C and end set 1700 °C, the peak point temperature is 1560°C. The latent heat of the sample is 0.631 J/kg.

Table 4 Summary of DSC for Granite Sample

Name of the Sample	Mass of the Sample (mg)	Thermal conductivity (w/mk)	Specific heat Capacity at 25°C (J/kg)	Latent heat of the sample (J/kg)
Wara	5.9000	2.99	790	0.5923
Yauri	5.9000	2.12	790	0.4343
Zuru	5.9000	3.12	790	0.631

4.0 DISCUSSION

4.1 Energy Dispersion X-Ray

From the ED-XRF all samples contain Fe_2O_3 , MgO , Al_2O_3 , K_2O , CaO and BaO as the major constituent with traces of minor element in negligible amount, the minor element include CuO , ZnO , Ga_2O_3 , HfO_2 , P_2O_5 , SO_3 , Cl , K_2O , Cr_2O_3 , MnO .

Observation on Table 1, 2 and 3 showed a weak variation in chemical composition despite their difference in location. It can be seen that the most predominant constituent is the silicon oxide, (40 – 50) wt. %, followed by the aluminum oxide which agree with work by (Aliyu *et al.*, 2023). It demonstrate that an increase in the amount of SiO_2 Contain in natural granite rock has silent effect on strength properties and micro – hardness. In granite samples value for iron oxide, of 2.521%, for Warrah 2.918% for Yauri and 2.244% for Zuru. This proved that Wara with the higher amount of iron oxide show stability over a wide range of temperature. It is concluded that iron oxide promotes crystallization of minerals in granite. The percentage of SiO_2 for Wara, Yawuri and Zuru are 50.09%, 54.22% and 53.035% respectively. While for Al_2O_3 it is 11.337%, 11.826% and 8.722% respectively. Based on the results there is little variation in the chemical composition, physical properties and thermal behaviours.

Observation on Figure 1 to 3 it display different element in different concentration and energy level. The element are Boron, Carbon, Copper, Manganese, Iron, Yttrium, Strontium, Zinc and Zirconium. It is also observed that Iron, Strontium and Zirconium are the element with higher concentration at different energy level.

4.2 DISCUSSION ON DSC RESULTS FOR GRANITE SAMPLES

From Table 4 it shown the specific heat capacity of granite sample measure at 25°C was found to be the same value for Wara, Yauri and Zuru granite samples which is 790 J/kg. The latent heat for Wara, Yauri and Zuru granite samples was presented in table 4 with the corresponding values of 0.5923 J/kg, 0.4343J/kg and 0.631J/kg respectively. Zuru granite sample is recommended for the formation thermal storage, because it has highest latent heat value which is 0.631J/kg follow by Wara with 0.5923J/kg and Yauri with lowest value of latent heat. The materials selection is based on the higher amount of latent heat and thermal conductivity which contribute to absorption and release of heat, during charging and discharging of heat as it reported by (Kakoko *et al.*, 2023), (Sharma *et al.*, 2023) and (Shanget *et al.*, 2020). From Table 4, it was discovered that Zuru granite sample has 3.12 w/mk conductivity which is highest followed by Wara with 2.99 w/mk and Yauri with 2.13 w/mk which has the lowest thermal conductivity. Materials of higher thermal conductivity absorb heat in small time interval and emit it at lower temperature. It's therefore Zuru granite is recommended for the formation of thermal storage.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

The thermo-physical properties of selected granite samples were tested with the views to determining its suitability as raw material for thermal storage. The research was concluded based on the following findings

- i. All granite samples contain Fe_2O_3 , MgO , Al_2O_3 , K_2O , CaO and BaO as the major constituent with traces of minor element in negligible amount, the minor element include CuO , ZnO , Ga_2O_3 , HfO_2 , P_2O_5 , SO_3 , Cl , K_2O , Cr_2O_3 , MnO
- ii. The specific heat capacity of granite sample measure at 25°C was found to be the same value for Wara, Yauri and Zuru granite samples which is 790 J/kg.

iii. The latent heat for Wara, Yauri and Zuru granite samples are 0.5923 J/kg, 0.4343J/kg and 0.631J/kg respectively.

5.1 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the above information from these research itsrecommended Zuru granites sample for the formation of thermal storage, becauseit's better thermal properties among other samples.

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